
SPIRITUAL FOUNDATIONS OF HUMANISM EDUCATION OF PRE-SCHOOL CHILDREN

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Abstract

In the article, the moral foundations of the humanistic upbringing of young children are touched upon, the differences between norms and values, the formation of humanistic relations in society, and the essence of the humanistic curriculum. It is noted that the humanist curriculum considers the student as a complete being, not subject to society, history and philosophy. If we look at the meaning of the experience of citizenship education, if we look at what its purpose is, we will see that it is related to norms such as a system of rules, but humanistic moral values are important for active and lively citizenship. When we look at the principles of humanism and the theory of humanistic education, we see that it originates from ancient traditions both in the West and in the East. From these traditions, various humanistic educational philosophies - classical, romantic, existentialist and critical philosophies - have developed. The article also reflects the theories on raising preschool children in a humanistic spirit.

Keywords: Humanism, traditions, structure, characterized, education.

Introduction. Humanistic education occupies an important place in the current social discourse. This is one of the themes that has always been present throughout the history of mankind. Historically, Azerbaijani and world thinkers expressed ideas about humanistic education, Nizami Ganjavi, Nasireddin Tusi, Muhammad Fizuli, Abbasgulu Agha Bakikhanov, Mirza Fatali Akhundzade wrote important works for educating the young generation in the spirit of humanism. The potential transmission of spiritual and moral values has always attracted attention. Therefore, ethics and values are the best legacy we can leave to future generations. Morality is a human condition, an ontological question, a process that makes us evaluate everything that happens to us, and allows us to value ourselves.

Moral education has a complex structure. The mechanism for moral education is in motion, each time more innovations are added to these mechanisms and new tools are launched to discover new mechanisms. However, the current reality poses some of the dangers that are the hallmark of postmodernity: our rush to achieve speed and efficiency can hide a basic sense of moral education beneath an excess of pedagogical techniques, strategies, and theory. Humanistic education of preschool children is a matter of instructions, rules, and pedagogical technique is a matter of conditions. We present them below. They are addressed to school education and mainly to teachers, professionals who are involved in the education of moral values of students every day.

Education and upbringing is a process of spiritual development that shapes human development. Educators' pedagogical views may stem from different worldviews, cultural experiences, and political ideas. There is a diversity of thought within humanism, and ideas develop in different cultural, social, and political settings. From a humanistic perspective, education focuses on the development of rationality, independence, empowerment, creativity, love and compassion. This

concern for humanity refers to relationships with other people. Valuing diversity and democracy are humane ways of living together.

The problem in humanist thought and action is the interrelation of autonomy and humanity. Autonomy is not an isolated individuality, but a relationship of one person to another. It implies the ability of the individual to take responsibility for his own life and ideas.

Humanism is a condition that allows people to develop human abilities, that is, to be a sensitive and communicative person, to acquire resources to live a good life, to live with moral values, and to help others to live a good life. It involves focusing on the development of the child's self-concept. If the child feels well, this is a positive start. Feeling good about yourself involves understanding one's strengths and weaknesses, and believing in one's ability to improve. Learning is not an end in itself; This is the means to move towards the peak of self-development, which Maslow called "Self-Actualization". A child learns because he is internally driven and gets his reward from the sense of accomplishment he gets after learning something. This differs from the behaviorist view, which expects extrinsic rewards to be more effective. Extrinsic rewards are rewards that come from the outside world, such as praise, money, gold stars, etc. Internal rewards come from within. This is consistent with the humanistic approach, where education is really about creating a need in the child or instilling in him his own motivation. Behavior is related to rewards received from others. Humanism is about rewarding yourself.

Much of the effort of a humanistic teacher should be spent on developing the child's self-esteem. It is very important for children to feel good about themselves (high self-esteem), to set appropriate goals and believe that they will achieve them (high self-efficacy). Organizing the teaching process in this way is known as child-centred teaching and is characterized by them taking responsibility for their own learning. Praise of positive

qualities and criticism of negative actions, in short, both praise and condemnation are rejected by humanists. A kind of addiction develops in children who work for the sake of hearing praise from their teachers. They strive for praise, and when their efforts are not recognized, they don't read and become passive. Therefore, if education prepares the child for future life, the humanistic approach is considered more correct.

Humanistic pedagogy is the theory and creative practice of personality education in children. Its main concept is spiritual humanism, the pedagogical process is determined by the system of content and tools derived from this concept. "Humanistic pedagogy implies a return to the individual, respect and trust in him, dignified attitude, acceptance of his personal goals, demands and interests" (Ilyasov, 2017). The main ideas of humanistic pedagogy are the following (Amonashvili, 1986):

- creation of spiritual unity with students through love, sincerity, understanding their wishes, cooperation and joint creativity;
- regulation of children's lives and upbringing with life itself;
- establishing relations with children on the basis of ongoing dialogue with promotion of ideas of equality and respect;
- to give children the opportunity to make free choices in various activities and communication;
- to follow the axiomatic norms of humanistic pedagogy: love - with love, kindness - with kindness, nobility - with nobility, personality - personality, etc.

A humanist teacher is not a spreader of knowledge, but a mediator. Traditional didactics implies a preference for participation and discovery methods, a process where the learner acquires knowledge through his own research, instead of memorizing everything the teacher says without understanding. "Approaching every student in terms of humanistic qualities in school life, which has become a living laboratory of the pedagogical process, should now be considered an important task for the activity of every teacher" (Bashirov, 2018). This is also related to the development of the skills and abilities of the students, and the tendency to comprehensively satisfy their needs in their daily life. A humanistic teacher is concerned with a child's affective (or emotional) needs in addition to their academic needs.

The humanistic curriculum, which aims at the development of the human personality, is of great importance in the formation of the student as a humanistic person. It perceives the learner as a complete being, not subject to society, history or philosophy. Experts in this field suggest that if education succeeds in developing the needs, interests, and abilities of each individual, learners will cooperate willingly and intelligently with each other for the common good. This will ensure the emergence of a free and universal society with common interests, not contradictions. Thus, humanists focus on individual freedom and democratic rights to create a global community based on the "common humanity of all people."

Although values and norms are usually mentioned together as terms in public discourse, they are actually

different concepts. Moral values are not personal preferences based on taste, but based on attitudes about what is good and what is bad, more or less clear and fully developed ideas about one's own life, social and natural environment. Moral values are emotionally charged cognitions related to behavior and these values guide behavior (Berkowitz, 1995; Oser, 1997; Veuglers & Vedder, 2003).

Moral values are a personal choice and cultural. Each person builds his own value configuration. Although it is more or less reactive, it is often secretive and hidden. Moral values give meaning to personal life. People who support the same values can unite in subcultures, ideologies, religions or other worldviews, live together and develop their common values.

Norms are different from moral values, they are included in rules. Norms are values-based, highly context-dependent, and have the attributes of agreements (Joas, 2002). Norms are developed in each group of society, such as the family, sports team, classrooms, local communities, the country, or the United Nations. It is a process in which the moral values of different participants struggle for hegemony. It is open communication and not competition (Mouffe, 2005; Castells, 2009; Todd, 2009). Unlike moral values, norms can be restrictive and a process that requires adaptation, while moral values are an individual process defined by each individual.

Me Education, which has a special role in the formation of moral and moral values, also stimulates the development of personal values and the development of social norms. It encourages people to construct their own values, engage in moral dialogues, and co-create norms. Focusing on values and norms, educational debates change over time (Apple, 1996; Goodson, 2005).

Conclusion. Humanization of education is one of the most urgent problems of today. Education of the young generation as an adult is the basis of humanistic education. It is also very important that educators regularly use appropriate forms and methods of communication and relationships with students. Humanistic education considers the student as a complete being. If education succeeds in developing the needs, interests and abilities of each individual, learners will cooperate willingly and intelligently with each other for the common good. This will ensure a free and universal society with shared interests, not conflict. Thus, humanists focus on individual freedom and democratic rights to create a global community based on the "common humanity of all people."

Moral and civic education strongly changes the attitude of the individual to the society. The process of education of rationality and personal responsibility is cursed by the individualization of society.

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